

Original Article

Acceptance of Cosmetic Surgery: A Comparative Analysis based on Gender, Religion and Geographical Locations

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Abstract

Cosmetic surgery involves enhancing, maintaining, and repairing a person's physical appearance through surgical procedures. This study employed a quantitative, cross-sectional survey design to examine acceptance levels of cosmetic surgery based on gender, place of residence, and religion. The study hypothesizes that acceptance is higher internationally than in Pakistan, females exhibit greater acceptance than males, and individuals of Islamic faith have lower acceptance than those of other religions. The Acceptance of Cosmetic Surgery Scale (ACSS) is used to assess participant's opinions. A total of 233 participants, aged 18 to 35, were recruited via convenience sampling through online surveys across Pakistan, the USA, the Middle East, Canada, Italy, and the UK. Data were analyzed using SPSS 25, employing t-tests to examine differences in acceptance based on demographics. Findings revealed significant differences in acceptance between individuals of Islamic faith and those of other religions ($t = -13.514, p < 0.01$) and between those residing in Pakistan and internationally ($t = -2.656, p < 0.05$). However, no significant gender-based difference was observed ($t = 0.169, p > 0.05$). These findings highlight cultural and religious influences on cosmetic surgery perceptions. Future research should explore additional variables and use qualitative approaches to gain deeper insights into the motivations and concerns surrounding cosmetic surgery.

Keywords: cosmetic surgery, gender, online survey, religion

INTRODUCTION

The field of plastic surgery which encompasses enhancement, maintenance, and restoration of a person's physical appearance by surgical techniques, is known as cosmetic surgery (Barone et al., 2017; Goh, C. L., 2009). The use of cosmetic surgery has grown globally, especially in Western countries. A 2020 report from the International Society of Aesthetic Plastic Surgery noted a 10.9% decrease in cosmetic surgery procedures due to widespread closures caused by COVID-19. Despite this, a recent poll by the American Society of Plastic Surgeons (ASPS) in 2022 revealed a significant rise in the demand for cosmetic procedures, with a proportion of 47% following the pandemic. Various factors contribute to the rise in cosmetic surgery (Pherson, 2005), such as increased confidence (Larson & Gosain, 2012), self-worth (Delinsky, 2005), and physical attractiveness (Sarwer et al., 1998). Another contributing factor is the growing media exposure (Sharp et al., 2014) of these treatments through both social and television media.

Previous research has extensively examined the impact of cosmetic surgery on self-esteem, quality of life, and body image. However, there remains a significant gap in the literature regarding how factors such as gender, religion, and geographical location influence the acceptance of cosmetic surgery. Although media influence is widely acknowledged as a major contributing factor in shaping access to and demand for cosmetic procedures, limited attention has been given to how gender and cultural factors, particularly religious beliefs, affect public attitudes toward such enhancements.

This study examines the acceptance of cosmetic surgery among individuals living in Pakistan, the Middle East, and a few Western countries who are between the ages of 18 and 35. It employs a quantitative, cross-sectional

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approach to examine views in relation to gender, religion affiliation, and geographic region. Age groups outside of this range and other psychosocial factors are not included in the research.

This study aims to address these gaps by investigating the acceptance of cosmetic surgery among different demographic factors, including gender and religious affiliation, and comparing attitudes across different geographic regions, including Western countries, the Middle East, and Pakistan. By analyzing the data, this research enhances comprehension of the global differences in acceptance of cosmetic surgery. The study posits that individuals belonging to the Islamic faith will exhibit less acceptance of cosmetic surgery compared to those of other religions (H1), females will demonstrate greater acceptance of cosmetic surgery than males (H2), and there will be higher acceptance of cosmetic surgery internationally compared to Pakistan (H3).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Umran & Demir (2020) conducted a study focusing on individuals' engagement in religious worship practices within the Islamic faith and their attitudes towards acceptance of aesthetic surgery. They found that active involvement in religious practices correlates with a negative view of cosmetic surgery, often considering it as contrary to religious principles. In contrast, individuals less engaged in religious practices tended to exhibit greater acceptance towards aesthetic procedures, reflecting varying attitudes influenced by religious beliefs.

Research by Kumar & Gupta (2018) explored the acceptability of cosmetic surgical procedures among the general population, highlighting a notable gender disparity. Their findings indicated that females generally exhibit higher levels of acceptance compared to males, which was further supported by a systematic review conducted by Alotaibi et al. (2021). This review concluded that females consistently demonstrate greater acceptance and knowledge of cosmetic surgery compared to their male counterparts, underscoring gender as a significant determinant of attitudes towards these procedures.

Studies conducted in Saudi Arabia and Pakistan (Arif et al., 2022; Alghonaim et al., 2019) has explored how media, including social and electronic platforms, impacts the acceptance and adoption of cosmetic surgery. They found a positive correlation between exposure to social media content related to cosmetic surgery and the adoption of such treatments. Sonmez & Eliyok (2022) emphasized that media not only sets beauty ideals but also significantly influences individuals' choices regarding cosmetic treatments. These findings underscore the powerful impact of media exposure on trends in cosmetic surgery and emphasize the need for a critical understanding of media's role in shaping beauty ideals and perceptions.

Wu et al. (2022) conducted a comparative study on attitudes towards cosmetic surgery across various cultural settings, finding that stronger body satisfaction correlates with increased acceptance of cosmetic procedures. This implies that individuals who view their bodies positively are more inclined to view cosmetic surgery favorably. Similar patterns were identified in Western societies, as documented by Swami et al. (2018), suggesting a widespread impact of body satisfaction on attitudes towards cosmetic enhancements.

Research conducted by Heidarzadeh et al. (2019), Asimakopoulou et al. (2019), and Khamseh & Nodargahfard (2020) explored how body image influences individuals' motivations for seeking cosmetic surgery. They found that individuals with lower perceived body image are more inclined to seek cosmetic enhancements as a means to improve their self-perception and overall well-being. These studies highlight body image improvement as a primary motivation driving individuals towards cosmetic surgery, underscoring its psychological significance in enhancing self-esteem and personal satisfaction.

Meta-analyses conducted by Kazeminia et al. (2023) and studies by Yoon & Kim (2020) consistently demonstrate that cosmetic surgery positively impacts psychological wellbeing. These studies suggest that engaging in cosmetic procedures can result in notable enhancements in self-esteem, self-assurance, and overall satisfaction with life. Such psychological benefits are crucial in understanding the broader implications of cosmetic surgery beyond physical enhancements, emphasizing its role in enhancing mental health and emotional well-being.

METHODS

Study Design

This research employed a quantitative, cross-sectional online survey approach, collecting data at a single point in time via an online platform, Google Forms.

Participants

The participants for the study were selected using a convenient sampling technique, they were approached using different online mediums with a restriction of receiving one response per participant. The study included a total of 233 participants, out of which 126 are females and 107 are males. The participants in the study are between 18 and 35 years of age.

Measures

The participant's attitudes toward cosmetic surgery were assessed using the Acceptance of Cosmetic Surgery Scale (ACSS), developed by Henderson-King & Henderson-King (2005). This scale comprises 15 items rated on a seven-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). 15 is the lowest possible score and 105 is the highest. The scale's item 10 has a reverse code. A higher score on this scale reflects higher acceptance of cosmetic surgeries. The internal consistency from the Henderson-King 2005 study proved to be high (Cronbach's alpha 0.91-0.93).

Procedure

The collection of data was done electronically, by creating a Google form. The participants were approached using several online mediums, e.g., Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp. Another approach was by spreading the forms among friends and family. A total number of 233 responses were recorded from several geographic locations, including The United States of America, the Middle East, Canada, Italy, and The United Kingdom, with a restriction to only fill one form per participant. A detailed description of the research was mentioned on the first page of the form, where the participants clicked the link voluntarily and with the knowledge that the data they provided would be kept private. Participants provided their consent to participate in the study, and their demographic information including age, gender, place of residence, religion, and annual income was collected. They completed the Acceptance of Cosmetic Surgery scale based on their preferences, and their responses were recorded.

Data Analysis

Data analysis in this study was conducted using SPSS 25 software. The independent samples t-test was utilized to examine differences in attitudes towards cosmetic surgery across genders, religions, and geographic locations. The results indicated significantly higher acceptance among participants from religions other than Islam (including Hinduism, Christianity, and Atheism), with a p-value of 0.000 and a mean difference of -33.60. Gender differences analysis showed no significant variation in acceptance between males and females, with a p-value of 0.866 and a mean difference of 0.56. Regarding geographic locations, participants residing internationally (including the USA, UK, Middle East, and Asia) showed higher acceptance compared to those residing nationally in Pakistan, with a mean difference of -8.688 and a significant p-value of 0.012. Statistical significance was defined as a p-value < 0.05.

RESULTS

Based on the study's findings, the first hypothesis demonstrated that individuals of other religions (Hinduism, Christianity, and Atheism) showed significantly higher acceptance of cosmetic surgery (Mean = 77.080) compared to those of the Islamic faith (Mean = 43.479), supporting the alternative hypothesis (H1) and rejecting the null hypothesis (H0). The t-test revealed a substantial mean difference of -33.601 between these groups, with a highly significant p-value ($p = 0.000$). Regarding the second hypothesis, no statistically significant difference was found in the acceptance of cosmetic surgery between females (Mean = 59.8889) and males (Mean = 59.3271), confirming the null hypothesis (H0) and refuting the alternate hypothesis (H2). The t-test showed a negligible mean difference of 0.561 between genders, with a non-significant p-value ($p = 0.866$). For the third hypothesis, individuals residing internationally (Mean = 62.688) exhibited significantly higher acceptance of cosmetic surgery compared to those residing nationally (Mean = 54.000), supporting the alternate hypothesis (H3) and rejecting the null hypothesis (H0). The t-test revealed a mean difference of -8.688 between these groups, with a significant p-value ($p = 0.012$).

Table 1:

Group Statistics

	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Islam	121	43.479	15.84356
Others	112	77.0804	21.44893

The group statistics for the two groups are shown in Table 1. 233 participants in total, 121 individuals belonging to the Islamic faith, and 112 individuals belonging to other faiths. In comparison to individuals belonging to the Islamic faith, which has a mean value of 43.479 and a standard deviation of 15.843, individuals belonging to other faiths have a higher mean value of 77.080 and a standard deviation of 21.448.

Table 2

T-test of means among individuals belonging to the Islamic faith and individuals belonging to other religious groups

Independent Sample T-test Results

	N	Mean Difference	T-value	Df	P-value	Lower	Upper
Islam	121	-33.601	-13.514	203.43	<0.01	-38.503	-28.698
Others	112						

Table 2 depicts the results of a t-test comparing the means of individuals belonging to the Islamic faith and individuals belonging to other religious faiths. The average difference between the two groups was -33.601. With 203.43 degrees of freedom (df), the computed tvalue for this comparison was -13.514. The p-value is less than 0.01, which indicates it is statistically significant. The confidence interval for the mean difference between the two groups may be calculated using the provided lower and upper values, -38.503 and -28.698, respectively.

Table 3:

Group statistics

	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Female	126	59.888	24.207
Male	107	59.327	26.347

The group statistics for the two groups are shown in Table 3. 233 participants in total, 126 females, and 107 males. In comparison to females, which have a mean value of 59.888 and a standard deviation of 24.207, males have a similar mean value of 59.327 and a standard deviation of 26.347.

Table 4:

T-test of means among females and males

Independent Sample T-test Results

	N	Mean Difference	T-value	Df	P-value	Lower	Upper
Females	126	0.561	0.169	231	>0.05	-5.968	7.092
Males	107						

Table 4 depicts the results of a t-test comparing the means of females and males. The average difference between the two groups was 0.561. With 231 degrees of freedom (df), the computed t-value for this comparison was 0.169. The p-value is greater than 0.01, which indicates it is statistically insignificant. The confidence interval for the mean difference between the two groups may be calculated using the provided lower and upper values, -5.968 and 7.092, respectively.

Table 5:

Group Statistics

	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
National (Pakistan)	82	54.000	22.580
International	151	62.688	26.018

The group statistics for the two groups are shown in Table 5. 233 participants in total, 82 individuals residing Nationally (Pakistan), and 151 individuals residing Internationally (the United States of America, the United Kingdom, the Middle East, and Asia). In comparison to National individuals, which have a mean value of 54.000 and a standard deviation of 22.580, International individuals have a higher mean value of 62.688 and a standard deviation of 26.018.

Table 6:
T-test of means among individuals residing Nationally and Internationally
Independent Sample T-test Results

	N	Mean Difference	T-value	Df	P-value	Lower	Upper
National (Pakistan)	82	-8.688	-2.656	187.320	<0.05	-15.142	-2.235
International	151						

Table 6 depicts the results of a t-test comparing the means of individuals residing Nationally (Pakistan) and individuals residing Internationally (the United States of America, the United Kingdom, the Middle East, and Asia). The average difference between the two groups was 8.688. With 187.320 degrees of freedom (df), the computed t-value for this comparison was 2.656. The p-value is smaller than 0.01, which indicates it is statistically significant. The confidence interval for the mean difference between the two groups may be calculated using the provided lower and upper values, -15.142 and -2.235, respectively.

Discussion

The primary purpose of this study was to explore the impact of gender and religious affiliation on levels of acceptance, while also comparing these attitudes across different geographic regions, namely Western countries, the Middle East, and Pakistan. Through this comparative framework, the research aimed to contribute to a broader understanding of how cultural and religious contexts shape public perceptions of cosmetic procedures. The study proposed that individuals adhering to the Islamic faith would exhibit lower acceptance of cosmetic surgery relative to followers of other religions (H1), that women would demonstrate greater acceptance than men (H2), and that international attitudes toward cosmetic surgery would reflect higher acceptance levels than those observed in Pakistan (H3).

The study's findings offer important insights into the acceptance of cosmetic surgery among various demographic groups. Firstly, our hypothesis (H1) that individuals adhering to the Islamic faith would exhibit less acceptance of cosmetic surgery compared to those from other religions was confirmed. This finding resonates with Muslu & Demir's (2020) research, which highlighted that strong religious engagement within Islam is associated with lower acceptance of cosmetic procedures, emphasizing how religious beliefs influence attitudes towards aesthetic treatments. These results are further supported by the work of Atiyeh et al. (2008), who noted that Islamic legal and ethical traditions tend to discourage non-essential cosmetic interventions. Within this framework, modifying the body for purely aesthetic purposes is often viewed as inconsistent with the belief that the human body is a divine trust that should not be altered without medical necessity. Conversely, a comparative theological study by Mavropoulos (2024) demonstrated that Christian traditions, especially within Catholic and Orthodox branches, tend to offer more complex and flexible interpretations. While certain denominations remain cautious about procedures rooted in vanity, others view cosmetic interventions aimed at physical restoration or self-care as ethically permissible within spiritual or aesthetic contexts.

The second hypothesis (H2) explored that women would exhibit higher levels of acceptance toward cosmetic surgery compared to men. Contrary to this expectation, the findings of the present study revealed no significant difference between male and female participants. This outcome stands in contrast to previous research conducted by Kumar & Gupta (2018) and Alotaibi et al., (2021), which found a greater inclination among women to pursue cosmetic procedures. The discrepancy may be attributed to evolving social norms, increasing media-driven emphasis on male aesthetics, or region-specific cultural factors that have altered traditional gender-based perceptions in more recent contexts.

The third hypothesis (H3) that there would be greater acceptance of cosmetic surgery internationally compared to Pakistan was supported. However, an analysis of the current academic literature reveals a lack of empirical studies that directly compare cosmetic surgery attitudes between Pakistani and international populations. This highlights a notable gap in cross-cultural research on aesthetic procedures. While it is commonly assumed that cosmetic surgery is more widely accepted in Western societies (Tam et al., 2012), possibly due to the influence of mass media, liberal beauty ideals, and individualistic cultural values, these assumptions have yet to be rigorously tested using comparative methods involving Pakistani samples. This finding highlights broader cultural influences on attitudes toward cosmetic surgery, which may not have been fully captured in some previous studies (Barone et al., 2017; Goh, 2009). Consequently, the present study offers valuable preliminary insight and underscores the need for future research that explores religious, cultural, and psychosocial factors in shaping perceptions of cosmetic procedures across diverse global settings.

In conclusion, this study utilized t-tests to examine attitudes towards cosmetic surgery across diverse demographic factors. The findings supported the hypotheses regarding lower acceptance among individuals of the Islamic faith and higher acceptance internationally compared to Pakistan. However, no gender differences were observed. This study contributes to the literature on cultural determinants of cosmetic surgery acceptance, highlighting both consistencies and contradictions in existing research and emphasizing the need for distinct approaches in understanding cultural influences on attitudes towards aesthetic procedures.

Limitations and Recommendations

The study on the acceptance of cosmetic surgery across different demographic factors is limited by its geographic focus on Western countries, the Middle East, and Pakistan, potentially missing diverse perspectives from regions like Africa, South America, and East Asia. Additionally, the analysis does not fully account for the wide cultural and religious diversity within these regions, which may lead to an oversimplified understanding of attitudes. The reliance on self-reported data introduces the risk of social desirability bias, and the cross-sectional design limits insights into how attitudes may evolve over time. Future research should expand geographically to include more diverse regions, delve deeper into cultural and religious differences, and adopt longitudinal designs to capture changes over time. Recommendations for diverse data collection methods, such as in-person interviews and paper surveys, should be implemented to enhance sample diversity and reduce biases. Exploring socio-cultural factors beyond religion, such as socio-economic status, education level, and access to healthcare, would provide a more comprehensive understanding of attitudes towards cosmetic surgery. Enhancing methodological rigor by employing strategies to mitigate bias in self-reported data, such as anonymous surveys and implicit attitude measures, would further improve the accuracy of the findings. These steps would contribute to broader cultural insights and a deeper understanding of global variations in cosmetic surgery acceptance.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the acceptance of cosmetic surgery across gender, religious affiliation, and geographic location. It found that individuals of the Islamic faith have significantly lower acceptance compared to those of other religions, and higher acceptance was observed internationally as compared to Pakistan, supporting our hypothesis. However, no significant differences were found between genders, contrary to our expectations. These findings emphasize the significant impact of religious beliefs on attitudes towards cosmetic surgery. The absence of gender disparities indicates changing societal norms. The study's constraints, such as biases in sampling and reliance on self-reported information, highlight the necessity for broader and more inclusive research approaches. In summary, this study identifies key demographic influences on cosmetic surgery acceptance and calls for further research to explore cultural and societal factors more deeply, enhancing our understanding of global variations in attitudes towards aesthetic procedures.

Disclosure Statement

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